

THE ROLE OF NITROGEN ON CARBON NANOTUBES-GRAFTED ACTIVATED CARBON FIBERS

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1 Introduction

Activated carbon fibers (ACFs) have the properties of small fiber diameters, large specific surface area, uniform pore size distributions and rapid adsorption/desorption rates, and have been widely used adsorbents. In addition, carbon nanotubes (CNTs) have received much attention recently because of their excellent mechanical and electrical properties and being candidates for adsorption. Thus, it should be highly interested as grafting CNTs onto ACFs to form a hybrid adsorbent, CNTs/ACFs [1]. Moreover, if the CNTs can be grown directly on the ACFs for using in the end applications, the post-synthesis processes of CNTs powders become unnecessary [2].

Using carbon fibers as substrates for the growth of CNTs have been observed in several studies. Carbon fibers are derived from several precursors, currently with polyacrylonitrile (PAN) being the predominant precursor. PAN-based carbon fibers generally have high strength, high modulus, and low density (1.75–2.00 g/cm³). Carbon fibers can also be made from pitch, where pitch-based carbon fibers tend to have a high modulus, as well as high thermal and electrical conductivities [3]. Fiber coating often used to modify the interfacial characteristics of carbon fibers, and improve the composites mechanical behavior.

There are mainly three different methods used for the synthesis of CNTs, including the electric arc discharge, laser ablation, and chemical vapor deposition (CVD). The electric arc discharge and laser ablation methods encounter problems in scaling up, while the CVD method provides the opportunities for the mass production of CNTs. The growth mechanism of CNTs on carbon fibers is generally regarded an “adsorption-diffusion-deposition” model. Thus, the key step to the production of CNTs is the adsorption and decomposition of hydrocarbons compounds (precursors of carbon atoms) on the active surface of catalyst nanoparticles. Therefore, the diameters of

the catalysts determine the feature of CNTs. The smaller the catalyst particles, the finer the CNTs and the fewer the number of the wall layers of CNTs. When the concentration of the precursor of catalyst is high, the reduced metal catalysts are more likely to agglomerate and grow up, resulting a large diameter of CNTs and enlarged diffusion path. This is not in favor of the synthesis of CNTs but will easily lead to the formation of amorphous carbons [4].

The floating catalyst method is more favorable for the growth of CNTs on carbon fibers comparing with thermal CVD method reported by other groups [5-6]. It decreases the inter-diffusion amount of the transition metal on the carbon surface while the contact time decreases between the transition metal and carbon fiber surface. At high growth temperatures (> 800 °C), the rapid inter-diffusion of the transition metal iron on the graphite surface results in a rough fiber surface with no CNTs grown on the surface. When the growth temperature is relatively low (650–800 °C), CNTs are fabricated on the graphite surface with catalytic particles on the nanotube top ends. [5]

Naito et al. [3] used the CVD methods making the CNTs grown on the carbon fiber surface. The results showed that grafting of CNTs improved the mechanical properties and the Weibull modulus of ultrahigh tensile strength PAN-based and ultrahigh modulus pitch-based carbon fibers. Specifically, the average tensile strength of the ultrahigh strength PAN-based carbon fibers grown with CNTs was 6.73 ± 1.01 GPa, which is 18 % higher than that in the as-received state (5.69 ± 1.02 GPa).

CNTs functionalized at the end caps with hexamethylene diamine (HMD) could be covalently grafted onto the surfaces of carbon fibers treated with acyl chloride, which increased the weight of carbon fiber by 1.2 %. The grafted CNTs were 50–200 nm in length and around 14 nm in diameter. [7] A similar chemical process was proposed by

Laachachi et al. [8] to graft CNTs onto a carbon fiber surface. CNTs and fibers were functionalized under acid or thermal treatments, leading to forming bonds between nanotubes and fibers such that the CNTs formed a 3D network around the carbon fibers. Grafting with acetone as a solvent gave the best results. However, this process would lead to CNTs bonding between two fibers. Moreover, the carbon fiber strands acted as filters and interfered with CNTs penetration. As a result, the CNTs could not graft homogeneously and cover completely on fiber surface. In addition, electrophoresis was utilized for the selective deposition of CNTs on woven carbon fabric [9]. The CNTs/carbon fabric/epoxy composites showed ~ 30 % enhancement of the interlaminar shear strength as compared to that of the composites without CNTs and demonstrated significantly improved out-of-plane electrical conductivity. Besides the carbon fibers, the ACFs have also been adopted as the substrate to grow the CNTs, taking advantage of the large amount of micropores of the ACFs to obtain a uniform dispersion of the nanosized catalytic metal ions [2].

Nitrogen-doped CNTs are known to exhibit good electrocatalytic activity for the oxygen reduction reaction (ORR) [10]. When CNTs were doped with nitrogen atoms through a replacement of carbon atoms, the local physical properties around the nitrogen atoms generated a significant change, resulting in the variation of the local chemical reactivity. This change increased the binding energy and the possibility of gas molecules interacting with the nitrogen-doped CNTs [11]. In addition, the chemical states of nitrogen atoms on the surface of nitrogen-doped CNTs contribute much more defect sites, which could be regarded as the micropores for adsorption.

The CNTs covering have been a widely used method for surface modification of carbon fibers for improving the interface shear strength between the carbon fiber and the matrix. However, the studies related to the characteristics and the applications of the CNTs grown on the ACFs are sparsely in literature. Therefore, the objective of this paper is to investigate the physicochemical properties of CNTs/ACFs and determine the role of nitrogen on CNTs/ACFs.

2 Experimental

2.1 Preparation of CNTs/ACFs

One commercial PAN-based ACFs sample manufactured by Taicarbon Inc. was used as starting materials (denoted as ACF), which was woven activated carbon fabric. The CVD method was used for growth of CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs directly onto ACFs (denoted as CNT/ACF or CN/ACF), through a cobalt/iron catalyzed reaction in a tubular furnace system. For CNT/ACF, the acetylene was used as the carbon source, and ferrocene as the catalyst precursor. After the ACFs sample immersed with cobalt (II) acetate ($\text{Co}(\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$) was positioned at the quartz tube in tubular furnace, a ceramic boat with ferrocene was placed in an appropriate position inside of the quartz tube. Then acetylene was directed into the tubular furnace at a rate of 20 sccm, reacting for 1 h at 650 °C in flowing argon gas. For CN/ACF, the acetonitrile was used as both the carbon and nitrogen sources, and ferrocene as the catalyst precursor. First, the mixture of acetonitrile and ferrocene were prepared with a ratio of $\text{Fe}/\text{C} = 1.3$ (w/w). After the ACF sample immersed with cobalt (II) acetate was positioned at the quartz tube in tubular furnace, the mixture was injected into the tubular furnace at a rate of 1.2 ml/h, reacting for 2 h at 900 °C in flowing argon gas. The as-grown CNT/ACF and CN/ACF were characterized without any treatment.

2.2 Characterization

The surface morphology and the transverse fracture surfaces of the samples were characterized using field emission scanning electron microscopy (FESEM). The FESEM samples were cut and attached to an aluminum stub with carbon tape and examined in a Hitachi S-4700, at an accelerating voltage of 5 kV. Elemental analysis (EA) was carried out using Elementar Vario EL III (Heraeus). The carbon (C), hydrogen (H), and nitrogen (N) contents of the samples of interest were determined directly using the thermal conductivity detector, and the others was then obtained by difference. Raman spectroscopy (RS) was carried out using a Renishaw - Ramascope, 1000 B system. The incident laser was an argon-ion laser at 514.5 nm. The Raman spectra from 500 to 3000 cm^{-1} were collected.

X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) was employed to determine the number and type of functional groups present on the surface of the samples. The XPS spectra of all samples were obtained using a spectrophotometer (ESCA PHI 1600). A twin anode Mg X-ray source ($h\nu = 1253.6$

eV) was used for this analysis, at a power of 15 kV at 400 W. The survey scans were collected from the binding energy of 0 to 1100 eV with a step size of 1 eV, in order to identify the elements present on the surface and in the sub-superficial zone of the samples. The XPS survey spectra exhibited prominent peaks due to carbon, nitrogen and oxygen only; consequently, the high-resolution XPS measurements were configured to include these three elements. The high-resolution spectra of C 1s, N 1s and O 1s were acquired over 280-300, 392-412 and 525-545 eV, with a step size of 0.1 eV. For calibration purposes, the C 1s electron binding energy corresponding to graphitic carbon was set at 284.6 eV. A nonlinear least squares curve fitting program (XPSPEAK software, Version 4.1) was used for XPS spectral deconvolution. A Shirley type background was chosen to be subtracted prior to quantification. After the baseline was subtracted, curve-fitting was performed using an asymmetrical Gaussian-Lorentzian sum function fitting program under an optimized peak shape. This peak-fitting procedure was repeated until an acceptable fit was obtained. It is assumed that the surface composition does not vary significantly along the tow of fibers, and that fiber heterogeneity is present but at a much smaller scale than the analysis area probed by the X-ray beams.

The surface structure of the samples were probed by N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms measured at -196 °C, carried out using a Micromeritics ASAP 2010 accelerated surface and porosimetry analysis system. Samples were outgassed at 350 °C overnight to remove adsorbed contaminants prior to the measurement. The specific surface area (SSA) of all samples was calculated using the standard Brunauer-Emmett-Teller (BET) method on eight points of the adsorption isotherm between $0.05 < P/P_0 < 0.31$. The total pore volume (V_t) was calculated by converting the amount adsorbed at a relative pressure of 0.99 to the volume of liquid adsorbate. Pore systems can be classified into three categories: macropore (> 50 nm), mesopore (2–50 nm) and micropore (< 2 nm) [12]. The micropore surface area (S_{mi}) and micropore volume (V_{mi}) were obtained by the t-plot method. The pore size distribution (PSD) curves of the samples in the mesopore region were determined from the desorption branches of the isotherms using the Barrett-Joyner-Halenda (BJH) method [13-14].

ASTM standard (ASTM D3379-75) were adopted in this study to determine the tensile strength of the samples. The tests were conducted on a testing

machine (CY-6040A4) with a cross-head speed of 1 mm/min. The gauge length of 20 mm was chosen and 10 specimens for each sample were successfully tested. The tab shape had an overall length about three times the specimen gage length and a width of about one half the gage length. All tested single-strand segments were representative and randomly taken from different yarns with care to retain the conformity of samples within the whole population.

3 Results and Discussion

The FESEM images of the samples are shown in Fig. 1. The diameter of one single fiber as-received was approximately 6.5 μm (Fig.1a) and the surface was smooth with small cracks (Fig.1b). The morphologies of CNT/ACF sample are shown in Fig. 1c-d. It can be observed that the CNTs with a high density and homogeneity were grown onto the single fibers of ACFs. A closer examination indicated that the spaghetti-like and a little randomly oriented CNTs were covered on the surface of ACFs. The average diameter of CNTs was 30-60 nm. Compared to CNT/ACF, the morphology of nitrogen-doped CNTs on ACFs looked different (Fig. 1e-f), where nanotubes were short, coarse and entangled, and the average diameter of nitrogen-doped CNTs was 25-83 nm. As shown in the FESEM images, it was suggested the tip-growth mechanism of CNTs and nitrogen-doped CNTs growth, agreed with that in the research of Sharma and Lakkad [15].

The EA was carried out to obtain the compositions of C, H, and N atoms in the samples. As seen from the data (Fig. 2), element C was the most abundant constituent in ACF (66.7 wt. %), CNT/ACF (68.5 wt. %) and CN/ACF (72.3 wt. %). Since the basal structure of PAN-based ACFs featured the C≡N groups, the data interpreted the N content of about 2.0 wt. % in the as-received ACF. Once the ACF covered with CNTs, the N content in the samples would decrease slightly. While the N content increased almost 50 % after grafting nitrogen-doped CNTs onto ACF, implying the N content contributed from the nitrogen-doped CNTs was significant. Except for C, H and N, the weight percent of the others decreased when the nanotubes were covered, especially for CN/ACF. It indicated that the grafting nitrogen-doped CNTs could decrease the oxygen content.

Fig. 3 shows the Raman spectra of the samples. The use of Raman spectroscopy to characterize composite interfaces can overcome some problems

about measuring directly the fiber stress or strain [16]. It was observed that the D ($\sim 1330\text{ cm}^{-1}$), the G ($\sim 1580\text{ cm}^{-1}$) and the G' ($\sim 2660\text{ cm}^{-1}$) bands of the carbon fiber spectrum shifted towards lower wavenumbers when the fibers were deformed in tension. Within the experimental data, it was not observed any significant change of the positions of the D and G bands. Additionally, the D and G bands are attributed to lattice defects and perfect hexagonal graphite, respectively. As a result, the intensity ratios of I_D/I_G can be considered an index of the degree of graphitization. The data showed that the ratio of I_D/I_G decreased when the ACF were covered with CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs. Especially, the CNT/ACF had the lowest value of I_D/I_G ratio (0.82) and exhibited another G' band, which was the typical feature of CNTs representing a high degree of graphitization.

The XPS survey scan spectra of the samples are shown in Fig. 4, which revealed the compositions of the most external surface. The major peaks observed in the scan spectra were due to the C1s, O1s, and N1s photoelectrons. The surface atomic ratios (O/C and N/C) derived from survey scan spectra were compared to see the nature of three samples. The O/C ratios were 0.159 (ACF), 0.037 (CNT/ACF) and 0.021 (CN/ACF), respectively. After the ACF grafted with CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs, the surface oxygen contents decreased significantly compared to as-received ACF. While the N/C ratios were 0.023 (ACF), 0.012 (CNT/ACF) and 0.044 (CN/ACF), respectively. This implies the CNTs on CNT/ACF were about a half coverage, and the cover of nitrogen-doped CNTs on ACF would enhance the nitrogen content on the fiber samples. These are in agreement with the results of the EA.

The high-resolution XPS spectra of the C 1s region were conducted. Carbon atoms differ in their binding energies depending on whether they are linked to one O atom by a single bond, a double bond, or two oxygen atoms [17]. As with all carbons, the C1s signals exhibited an asymmetric tailing, which was partially due to the intrinsic asymmetry of the graphite peak or to the contribution of oxygen surface complexes. Deconvolution of the C1s spectra gives at most seven individual component groups that represent carbon atoms in polyaromatic structures ($C(sp^2)$, B.E. = 284.6 eV) and in aliphatic structures ($C(sp^3)$, B.E. = 285.4 eV), and carbon present in phenol, alcohol, ether or C = N groups (B.E. = 286.0 eV), carbonyl or quinone groups (B.E. = 287.6 eV), carboxyl, lactone or ester groups (B.E.

= 288.8 eV), carbonate groups (B.E. = 290.6 eV), and shake-up satellite peaks due to $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions in aromatic rings (B.E. = 291.6 eV) [18].

Table 1 summarizes the calculated percentages of graphitic and functional carbon atoms. The carboxyl and phenolic groups were the most predominant functionalities on the surface of the samples, though the percent of oxygen-containing groups decreased as the ACF grafted with CNTs. Moreover, compared with the pristine ACF, these multi-scale composites resulted in the increase of defect sites ($C(sp^3)$) and $\pi-\pi^*$ transitions in aromatic rings. The content of the satellite peaks caused by $\pi-\pi^*$ shake-up responded to the change in structure. It is evident that the conjugated systems have become much stabilized as the CNTs grown on the surface of ACF. This implies the generation of these defect sites attributed to the coverage of CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs remained the stability of structure.

The deconvolution of XPS O1s peaks gives additional information on the nature of the surface oxygen-containing groups of samples. The optimum curve fitting of the O1s peak for all samples, shown in Table 2, indicates four different O functionalities and the contribution of chemisorbed water can be identified [19-20]. The peak at 531.1 eV corresponds to the carbonyl oxygen atoms (O_{G1}); the peak at 532.3 eV to the carbonyl oxygen atoms in esters, amides and anhydrides as well as oxygen atoms in hydroxyls or ethers (O_{G2}); the peak at 533.3 eV to the ether oxygen atoms in esters and anhydrides (O_{G3}); and the peak at 534.2 eV to the oxygen atoms in the carboxyl groups (O_{G4}). The contribution of chemisorbed water located at 536.1 eV (H_2O) is found except for the CN/ACF.

The predominant oxygen functionalities on the surface of the pristine ACF were carboxyl groups. The coverage of CNTs generated the increase in the percent of C=O groups significantly but decrease in the percent of -COOH groups. It is noteworthy that the ACF covered with nitrogen-doped CNTs had completely different behaviors of oxygen functionalities. To sum up, the grafting of CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs on ACF changed the predominant species to carbonyl groups. It is observed that ACF exhibited very much high percentage of chemisorbed water, but it decreased significantly when the CNTs grafted on ACF, and even disappeared on CN/ACF. This implies the chemisorbed water was highly dependent on the surface oxides.

The high resolution XPS N 1s spectra were obtained to identify the type and distribution of nitrogen functionalities by the curve-fitting procedures. Contrary to C 1s and O 1s spectra, the shape of N 1s profiles was relatively irregular. According to the existing literature data [21-23], the N 1s spectra were decomposed into at most seven identified components: the peak at 395.7 eV (N_{G1}) ascribed to nitride-like species or aromatic N-imines; the peak at 398.4 eV (N_{G2}) attributed to pyridine-like structures; the peak at 400.1 eV (N_{G3}) to the nitrogen atoms in pyrrolic or amine moieties; the peak at 401.2 eV (N_{G4}) containing a contribution from quaternary or protonated nitrogen; the peak at 402.4 eV (N_{G5}) to the nitrogen atoms in pyridine-N-oxides; the peak at 404 eV (N_{G6}) attributed to shake-up satellites; and the peak at 405 eV (N_{G7}) ascribed to chemisorbed nitrogen oxides.

For the pristine ACF, the calculated percentages of functional N atoms (Table 3) indicated that pyridine-type N groups (N_{G2}) and quaternary or protonated nitrogen (N_{G4}) were the predominant functionalities. The percentages of the NO_x-containing groups (N_{G5} and N_{G7}) decreased when the CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs grown on ACF, agreed with the previous discussion. Since the N atoms were contributed from the ACF for CNT/ACF, most of the distributions of N-functionalities were similar to that on ACF. But the introduction of CNTs would result in the increase of pyridine-like structures (N_{G2}) and the shake-up satellites (N_{G6}). The N atoms on CN/ACF were contributed both from the nitrogen-doped CNTs and ACF. Compared to CNT/ACF, the increase in the pyridine-like structures (N_{G2}) and the nitrogen atoms in pyrrolic or amine moieties (N_{G3}) but decrease in the pyridine-N-oxides (N_{G5}) and the shake-up satellites (N_{G6}) were observed in CN/ACF. This result indicated the nature of nitrogen-doped CNTs grown on ACFs. Specifically, a majority of N atoms were present in the six-member rings located at the edges of the graphene layers as pyridinic-N (N_{G2}) where N is linked to sp² carbon atoms, or in the interior as quaternary-N (N_{G4}) where N is linked to three sp² carbon atoms. In particular, nitrogen-doped CNTs were characterized by the pyridine-like structures of six-member rings (N_{G2}) and hydrophobicity due to deficiency of oxygen atoms.

Fig. 6 shows N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms of the samples at -196 °C. It can be seen that the adsorption isotherms for ACF and CN/ACF were essentially type I according to the BET classification and the desorption branch almost superimposed on

the adsorption branch, indicative of microporosity. It should be noteworthy that the isotherms of the CNT/ACF featured with a hysteresis loop. The existence of hysteresis loop clearly over $P/P_0 > 0.45$ implied some tubes had two accessible ends [24] and CN/ACF could be regarded as the porous materials characterized by microporosity/mesoporosity [25]. According to IUPAC classification, it can be recognized as Type H4, which has been obtained with samples having capillary space between parallel plates or open slit-shaped capillaries. It is interesting that this type of hysteresis loop particularly occurred on CNT/ACF but not on CN/ACF. A possible reason is that the defect sites (micropores) on the surface of nitrogen-doped CNTs have destroyed the integrity of the walls such that the structures of slit-shaped capillaries were overwhelmed by the microporosity contributed from the defect sites of N-functionalities.

Table 4 lists the surface structure data for all samples. As seen from the data, compared to that of ACF, 69 % or 80 % of the SSA were observed on CNT/ACF and CN/ACF, and 76 % or 81 % of V_t were observed on CNT/ACF and CN/ACF. As a result, the CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs grown on ACF tended to slightly decrease the microporosity, especially for CNT/ACF. Moreover, the ratios of S_{mi}/SSA were 0.72 (ACF), 0.65 (CNT/ACF), and 0.67 (CN/ACF), respectively. The ratios of V_{mi}/V_t were 0.70 (ACF), 0.57 (CNT/ACF), and 0.65 (CN/ACF), respectively. These ratios also support the previous discussion. It is known that the open state of the CNTs is an essential factor for the presence of the hysteresis loop. And the tip-growth mechanism of CNTs growth were suggested from the examination of FESEM images. Therefore, it is speculated that the ends of CNTs were closed and the hysteresis loop was attributed to the intertubular space. And also the fact that closed ends of nanotubes were present, the SSA and V_t decreased after coverage of CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs on ACF.

The development of porosity after modifications could be recognized from the PSD curves, shown in Fig. 7, calculated by the BJH method. The patterns of PSD curves for all samples were similar, but a significant difference on the average pore sizes of 3-4 nm was observed. This should be the effect due to the CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs growth, mostly the contribution from the intertubular spaces of the aggregated CNTs [26].

The results of the tensile test on the samples were shown in Table 5, where the data were obtained

from ten replicate experiments. A yarn contained about 756 ± 32 fibers from the examination of FESEM. The transverse fracture surfaces of each yarn after tensile test were randomly taken from 5 different filaments and characterized using FESEM. Then the tensile strengths could be calculated. As seen from Table 5, the high temperature processes of CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs growth have made the decrease in the diameter of ACF. The transverse fracture surfaces were smooth and belonging to brittle fracture. The CN/ACF exhibited the highest tensile strength, 33 % higher than that of ACF. Though the tensile strength of CNT/ACF was a little lower than that of pristine ACF, the high temperature CNTs growth on ACF did not significantly destroy the strength of ACF.

4 Conclusions

The nanotubes could be successfully grown on the surface of ACF without significant catalysts residue on the surface of ACF. The examination of FESEM suggested the tip-growth mechanism of CNTs and nitrogen-doped CNTs growth. The spaghetti-like and a little randomly oriented CNTs were uniformly covered on the surface of ACF. While the morphology of nitrogen-doped CNTs on ACF was short, coarse and entangled. The N content increased almost 50 % after grafting nitrogen-doped CNTs onto ACF; moreover, the grafting nitrogen-doped CNTs could decrease the oxygen content for the composites. The degree of graphitization has improved and the conjugated systems have become much stabilized when the CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs grown on ACF, even though the existence of defect sites due to N-functionalities. The growth of CNTs or nitrogen-doped CNTs on ACF changed the predominant surface oxides to carbonyl groups. A majority of N atoms were present in the six-member rings located at the edges of the graphene layers as pyridinic-N where N is linked to sp^2 carbon atoms, or in the interior as quarternary-N where N is linked to three sp^2 carbon atoms. The nitrogen-doped CNTs on ACF were characterized by the pyridine-like structures of six-member rings and hydrophobicity due to deficiency of oxygen atoms. The defect sites on the surface of nitrogen-doped CNTs destroyed the integrity of the walls such that the structures of slit-shaped capillaries were overwhelmed by the microporosity contributed from the defect sites of N-functionalities. As a result, for both CNT/ACF and CN/ACF, N atoms could enhance the π -bond on nanotubes and hence make the nanotubes more

stable. Moreover, grafting nitrogen-doped CNTs could improve the mechanical strength of 33 %.

References

- [1] R.J. Mora, J.J. Vilatela and A.H. Windl "Properties of composites of carbon nanotube fibres". *Composites Science and Technology*, Vol. 69, pp. 1558–1563, 2009.
- [2] S.S. Tzeng, K.H. Hung and T.H. Ko, "Growth of carbon nanotubes on activated carbon fiber fabrics," *Carbon*, Vol. 44, pp. 859-865, 2006.
- [3] K. Naito, J.M. Yang, Y. Tanaka and Y. Kagawa, "Tensile properties of carbon nanotubes grown on ultrahigh strength polyacrylonitrile-based and ultrahigh modulus pitch-based carbon nanotubes," *Applied Physics Letters*, Vol. 92, pp. 231912, 2008.
- [4] J. Zhao, L. Liu, Q. Guo, J. Shi, G. Zhai, J. Song and Z. Liu, "Growth of carbon nanotubes on the surface of carbon fibers," *Carbon*, Vol. 46, pp. 380-383, 2008.
- [5] S. Zhu, C.H. Su, S.L. Lehoczy, I. Muntele and D. Ila, "Carbon nanotube growth on carbon fibers," *Diamond and Related Materials*, Vol. 12, pp. 1825–1828, 2003.
- [6] W.Z. Li, D.Z. Wang, S.X. Yang, J.G. Wen, Z.F. Ren, "Controlled growth of carbon nanotubes on graphite foil by chemical vapor deposition," *Chemical Physics Letters*, Vol. 335, pp. 141–149, 2001.
- [7] X. He, F. Zhang, R. Wang and W. Liu, "Preparation of a carbon nanotubes/carbon fiber multi-scale reinforcement by grafting multi-walled carbon nanotubes onto the fibers," *Carbon*, Vol. 45, pp. 2559-2563, 2007.
- [8] A. Laachachi, A. Vivet, G. Nouet, B.B. Doudou, C. Poilâne, J. Chen, J. Bo bai and M. Ayachi, "A chemical method to graft carbon nanotubes onto a carbon fiber," *Materials Letters*, Vol. 62, pp. 394–397, 2008.
- [9] E. Bekyarova, E.T. Thostenson, A. Yu, H. Kim, J. Gao, J. Tang, H.T. Hahn, T.W. Chou, M.E. Itkis and R.C. Haddon, "Multiscale Carbon Nanotube-Carbon Fiber Reinforcement for Advanced Epoxy Composites" *Langmuir*, Vol. 23, pp. 3970-3974, 2007.
- [10] C.V. Rao, C.R. Cabrera and Y. Ishikawa "In search of the active site in nitrogen-doped carbon nanotube electrodes for the oxygen reduction reaction". *The Journal of Physical Chemistry Letters*, Vol. 1, pp. 2622-2627, 2010.
- [11] S. Peng and K. Cho "Ab initio study of doped carbon nanotube sensors". *Nano Letters*, Vol. 3, No. 4, pp. 513-517, 2003.
- [12] IUPAC Manual of Symbols and Terminology, 1972.
- [13] Z.T. Liu, C.X. Wang, Z.W. Liu and J. Lu, "Selective hydrogenation of cinnamaldehyde over Pt-supported multi-walled carbon nanotubes: Insights into the tube-size effects", *Applied Catalysis*, Vol. A344, pp. 114-123, 2008.

- [14] L. Li, G. Wu and B.Q. Xu, "Electro-catalytic oxidation of CO on Pt catalyst supported on carbon nanotubes pretreated with oxidative acids," *Carbon*, Vol. 44, pp. 2973-2983, 2006.
- [15] S.P. Sharma and S.C. Lakkad, "Morphology study of carbon nanospecies grown on carbon fibers by thermal CVD technique," *Surface and Coatings Technology*, Vol. 203, pp. 1329-1335, 2009.
- [16] M.A. Montes-Morán and R.J. Young, "Raman spectroscopy study of high-modulus carbon fibres: effect of plasma-treatment on the interfacial properties of single-fibre-epoxy composites, Part II: Characterisation of the fibre-matrix interface," *Carbon*, Vol. 40, pp. 857-875, 2002.
- [17] H.P. Boehm, "Surface oxides on carbon and their analysis: A critical assessment," *Carbon*, Vol. 40, pp. 145-149, 2002.
- [18] C. Moreno-Castilla, M.V. Lopez-Ramon and F. Carrasco-Marin, "Changes in surface chemistry of activated carbons by wet oxidation," *Carbon*, Vol. 38, pp. 1995-2001, 2000.
- [19] U. Zielke, K.J. Huttinger and W.P. Hoffman, "Surface-oxidized carbon fibers: I. surface structure and chemistry," *Carbon*, Vol. 34, pp. 983-998, 1996.
- [20] U. Zielke, K.J. Huttinger and W.P. Hoffman, "Surface-oxidized carbon fibers: II. chemical modification," *Carbon*, Vol. 34, pp. 999-1005, 1996.
- [21] S. Biniak, G. Szymanski, J. Siedlewski and A. Swiatkowski, "The characterization of activated carbons with oxygen and nitrogen surface groups," *Carbon*, Vol. 35, pp. 1799-1810, 1997.
- [22] E. Pamula and P.G. Rouxhet, "Bulk and surface chemical functionalities of Type III PAN-based carbon fibers," *Carbon*, Vol. 41, pp. 1905-1915, 2003.
- [23] E. Raymundo-Pinero, D. Cazorla-Amoros and A. Linares-Solano, "The role of different nitrogen functional groups on the removal of SO₂ from flue gases by N-doped activated carbon powders and fibers," *Carbon*, Vol. 41, pp. 1925-1932, 2003.
- [24] E.B. Mackie, R.A. Wolfson, L.M. Arnold, K. Lafdi and A.D. Migone, "Adsorption studies of methane films on catalytic carbon nanotubes and on carbon filaments," *Langmuir*, Vol. 13, pp. 7197-7201, 1997.
- [25] S. Inoue, N. Ichikuni, T. Susuki, T. Uematsu and K. Kaneko, "Capillarity condensation of N₂ on multiwall carbon nanotubes," *Journal of Physical Chemistry*, Vol. B102, pp. 4689-4692, 1998.
- [26] K. Yang and B. Xing, "Desorption of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons from carbon nanomaterials in water," *Environment Pollution*, Vol. 145, pp. 529-537, 2007.

Fig. 1. FESEM images of the samples.

Fig. 2. Elemental components of the samples.

Fig. 3. Raman spectra of the samples.

Fig. 4. XPS survey scan spectra of the samples.

Fig. 5. Surface atomic ratios of the samples.

Fig. 6. Adsorption isotherms of N_2 at 77 K for the samples.

Fig. 7. Pore size distributions of the samples.

Table 1. Results of the fits of the XPS C 1s region, values given in at. % of total intensity

Sample	Binding energy (eV)						
	284.6	285.4	286.0	287.6	288.8	290.6	291.6
	C (sp ²)	C (sp ³)	-OH	C=O	-COOH	Carbonates	$\pi \leftrightarrow \pi^*$
ACF	44.4	37.9	2.7	1.8	5.0	2.4	5.8
CNT/ACF	44.8	40.4	—	0.7	4.2	1.8	8.1
CN/ACF	43.8	38.8	1.9	0.6	2.8	2.1	10.0

Table 2. Results of the fits of the XPS O 1s region, values given in at. % of total intensity

Sample	Binding energy (eV)				
	531.1	532.3	533.3	534.2	536.1
	C=O (O _{G1})	R-O-C=O, O=C-NH ₂ , O=C-O-C=O, -OH, R-O-R (O _{G2})	R-O-C=O, O=C-O-C=O (O _{G3})	-COOH (O _{G4})	H ₂ O
ACF	10.5	4.0	11.8	36.5	37.2
CNT/ACF	68.6	6.5	10.6	2.3	12.0
CN/ACF	71.3	11.7	1.5	15.5	—

Table 3. Results of the fits of the XPS N 1s region, values given in at. % of total intensity

Sample	Binding energy (eV)						
	395.7	398.4	400.1	401.2	402.4	404	405
	Nitride-like species or aromatic N-imines (N _{G1})	Pyridine -type N (N _{G2})	Pyrrolic or amine moieties (or Pyrrole, Pyridone) (N _{G3})	Quarternary N (N _{G4})	Pyridine -N oxides (N _{G5})	Shake-up satellites (N _{G6})	NO ₂ (N _{G7})
ACF	3.2	25.6	10.9	21.9	12.7	—	25.7
CNT/ACF	—	31.8	6.0	21.7	7.7	10.8	22.0
CN/ACF	2.6	36.3	8.4	21.2	2.5	6.3	22.7

Table 4. Surface structure of the MWNTs determined from N₂ adsorption/desorption isotherms

Sample	SSA (m ² /g)	S _{mi} ^α (m ² /g)	V _t ^γ (cm ³ /g)	V _{mi} ^η (cm ³ /g)	V _{me} ^φ (cm ³ /g)	Mean pore size ^ζ (nm)
ACF	886	639	0.4395	0.3076	0.0758	1.98
CNT/ACF	607	392	0.3349	0.1896	0.103	2.21
CN/ACF	709	478	0.3577	0.2312	0.0722	2.02

^α S_{mi} was determined by t-plot method.

^γ V_t represents the single point total pore volume at P/P₀ ≈ 0.99.

^η V_{mi} was determined by t-plot method.

^φ V_{me} was calculated by BJH method.

^ζ Mean pore size was obtained by 4V_t/SSA.

Table 5. Results of tensile tests for the samples

Sample	Max. loading (N) (n = 10)	diameter of filament (μm) (n = 5)	Total cross-sectional area (mm ²)	Tensile strength (MPa)
ACF	3.0 ± 0.4	6.6 ± 0.2	0.02586	116.0
CNT/ACF	2.5 ± 0.2	6.5 ± 0.1	0.02509	99.6
CN/ACF	3.3 ± 0.3	6.0 ± 0.2	0.02138	154.3